

NUTRI•KNOW

STRUVITE (IT)

RENURE (BE)

GAS LOOP (IT)

POCKETBOER 2 (BE)

SOS_AQUAE (IT)

Grass2Algae (BE)

FERTICOOP-GO (ES)

MOPS (IE)

Manure Management Tool (ES)

Duncannon Blue Flag Farming (IE)

Manure Concentrator (ES)

Biorefinery Glas (IE)

Exchanging easy-to-understand nutrient management knowledge with farmers

NUTRI-KNOW aims to improve nutrient management practices in agriculture by establishing an ongoing cycle of knowledge exchange for the benefit of both farmers and the environment.

Slurry Concentrator

a smart investment to reduce transport costs

Why consider this innovation?

If you're a livestock **farmer** handling large volumes of slurry and facing high transport costs, a **slurry concentrator can help you reduce expenses**, improve nutrient application, and make better use of your resources.

The slurry concentrator separates raw slurry into:

- A **concentrated fraction**: smaller in volume, but rich in nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus - ideal for transport to distant fields.
- A **diluted fraction**: mostly water, which can be applied on nearby land.

You can **use your existing slurry tanker and tractor to apply both fractions**, which keeps costs low and operations simple.

What is the investment?

Equipment Type	Initial Cost
Automated concentrator	€40,000
Manual concentrator	€29,000

Annual operational costs

- Cleaning and maintenance: ~€300/year
- Motor replacement (every 4 years): ~€100/year
- Energy use per m³ of slurry:
 - Sow slurry: €0.018/m³
 - Fattening pig slurry: €0.035/m³

When do I start saving money?

Savings depend on how much slurry you treat and your farm's average transport distance. According to real case data (average transport distance = 135 km):

- With **sow slurry**, you start saving when you treat **>350 m³/year**
- With **fattening pig slurry**, you start saving when you treat **>500 m³/year**

At **1,000 m³/year**, annual savings can reach **up to €900** - mostly due to reduced transport costs and better nutrient use.

Practical Recommendation: The larger your farm, the faster the return. The system can also handle both types of slurry without modifications.

View of the concentrator

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our journey!**

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